

Holographic QECC mechanism leads to the inflationary universe

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Holographic QECC mechanism leads to the inflationary universe in the classicalization process. This is a companion piece to a previous article titled “Gravity is the ‘Classicalized’ Entanglement”. Validation of the theory scheme needs concrete work.

I Holographic QECC mechanism leads to the inflationary universe in the classicalization process

Quantum information has come to play a fundamental role in emergent gravity, but the desired theory is still far away. There seems to be missing a crucial piece and a general theory scheme, which we argue to be the entanglement-energy relation and the classicalization process, respectively.

While the space emerging from vacuum entanglement structure (modeled by holographic tensor network) is completely quantum when we think about the origin of the universe, the emergent time and locality through quantum fluctuation measurement are the signatures of classicality, i.e., there is no time and locality in the completely quantum regime. Gravity could not be completely quantum in this sense, and the effort trying to completely quantize gravity might be in the wrong direction. How do time and locality emerge from the vacuum? We turn to the Holographic QECC mechanism and find

We argue that spontaneous quantum field excitation in vacuum bulk can be seen as information erasure (in this sense, we argue that, in our universe, the vacuum has the maximal information (uncertainty) density), which can be restored via holographic QECC. The QECC mechanism inherently incorporated into the vacuum indicates the information unitarity of the whole universe. The ongoing classicalization process, which includes spontaneous quantum field excitation, continuously erases information. Consequently, a broader boundary is needed for the holographic QECC mechanism to be effective and preserve information unitarity. This helps us to imagine the visage of the early universe, maybe even the original universe. In conclusion, holographic QECC mechanism leads to the inflationary universe in the classicalization process. Our universe exists as the most ambitious quantum error correction code. The universe starts from vacuum chaos and goes back to vacuum chaos, over and over again. The recurrence time of such a cycle seems to be infinite.

The randomness of quantum fluctuations might be the reason why holographic random tensor network model works well in describing emergent space and reproducing the RT formula. Holographic duality from random tensor networks.

II The Theory Scheme

Below is the article titled “Gravity is the ‘Classicalized’ Entanglement”.

Abstract: This is an outline of a theory scheme trying to reconcile gravity and quantum mechanics. The theory scheme is quantum in its origin, but with classicality mechanism inherent in it. There is always a classicalization tendency in quantum vacuum space governed by uncertainty principle. Therefore, instead of quantizing the seemingly classical entities, we propose starting from the completely quantum regime and figure out the classicality mechanism leading to the current universe. We argue that the eternal quantum vacuum works as the one and only perpetual motion machine through spontaneous quantum fluctuation measurement, powering the classicalization process, which we define as the less entanglement process. At first, all information is contained in the quantum vacuum. Along with the classicalization process, such as quantum field excitation and thermal effects, area law transitions to apparent volume law. In this sense, the existence of holographic principle is natural. Starting from holographic (random) tensor network model, we argue that the origin of space is completely quantum, while time and locality emerging through quantum fluctuation measurement are signatures of classicality. In this context, we conjecture that gravity is the ‘classicalized’ entanglement. From the perspective of quantum vacuum fluctuation engines, we propose an entanglement-energy-information conservation law. This theory scheme serves as a cosmological model of the origin and evolution of the universe, implying a solution to the cosmological constant problem. In the development of this theory scheme, we witness the emergence of physics-mathematics correspondence and claim that mathematics has a physical origin. This theory scheme is consistent with existing theories and cosmological observations as far as we know.

Imagining in the early universe, the whole universe is totally (or maximally) entangled, the inseparable one and only (mathematically, the trivial topology). The universe is the one and only observer. It is a completely quantum vacuum and there are only several fundamental entities: entanglement, energy, information and quantum fluctuations. Through the holographic tensor network model, space geometry emerges from the entanglement structure of the quantum vacuum, i.e., the origin of space geometry is completely quantum, which could lead to the Reeh-

Schlieder theorem [1].

In this early universe, the concept of system-environment does not exist and there is no notion of time and observer locality. They can not exist in this completely quantum regime because of the entanglement structure. However, classicality exists in the current universe. Where does the classicality come from? We argue that classicality is inherent to the quantum vacuum because of quantum fluctuation (we can not strictly distinguish between quantum and classical), and time and locality are signatures of classicality.

First of all, we need to establish the relationship between energy and entanglement, which we show naturally leads to the emergent time and locality through quantum fluctuation measurement. For quantum many-body systems with maximally entangled ground states, there is a minimum separable energy for the set of separable states, which is strictly greater than the ground state energy [2], i.e., less entanglement leads to a higher energy level. This principle is utilised in the design of many-body quantum vacuum fluctuation engines, an engine cycle whereby work is extracted from the quantum vacuum via local measurements [3]. How do such measurement-powered machines exist in our universe? The core question is the natural existence of local measurement, and indeed, quantum fluctuation serves as local measurement. It was shown that a quantum mean field could be decohered by its own quantum fluctuations, an example of how a quantum ‘system’ emerges and is viewed as effectively open and decoheres through its own dynamics [4].

We refer to this transition of the totally entangled universe to separable systems as the (open) system-environment mechanism (mathematically, the advent of non-trivial topology), which leads to the emergence of time and locality in the context of the Page-Wootters formalism [5, 6]. In other words, time and locality emerge when separability comes into existence, which indicates less entanglement. The less entanglement process, we define, is the classicalization process. Back to the theory of quantum vacuum fluctuation engine, the local measurement leads to quantum field excitation (particle creation), which we conclude belongs to the classicalization process. In this spirit, our theory scheme encompasses the Higgs boson and we conjecture that gravity is the classicalized entanglement.

In summary, we have argued that time and locality are signatures of classicality, and the origin of space is completely quantum. This difference of space and time in their origins could be the fundamental reason why we perceive the two as distinguished entities. So far, all endeavours have been aimed at finding a theory of quantum gravity, searching for graviton and quantizing the seemingly classical entities. In our theory scheme, we propose that this endeavour might be pointless. Gravity emerges in the classicalization process and is not completely quantum. Maybe the best we can expect is a semiclassical theory of gravity and endeavours should be devoted to the understanding of the classicalization pro-

cess. In the classicalization process, space and time intertwine with each other and form the spacetime manifold, which is described by general relativity. The ability to derive Einstein’s equations could be a major landmark of our theory scheme.

In this theory scheme, we witness the emergence of a physics-mathematics correspondence in the classicalization process, by just considering how the math grows in it. We claim that mathematics has a physical origin. We wonder about its relation to mirror symmetry in string theory. This duality and the unification of mathematics and physics could help us to explore the origin and evolution of the universe.

III Implications and Open Questions

1. Through the triangle relation: geometry—(related by the RT formula)—entanglement—(related by CFT)—energy-momentum, the area of the extremal surface is related to the energy-momentum distribution at the boundary, which turns out to be equivalent to the linearized Einstein equation [7, 8]. This derivation of linearized Einstein equation works for small perturbations around the vacuum. We expect this derivation to be the supporting evidence for our theory scheme by reinterpretation.

2. In the classicalization process (evolution of the universe), the vacuum entanglement structure exists eternally. We argue that the emergent gravity can still preserve some quantumness through an unknown mechanism. Consequently, gravity can still induce entanglement between two massive particles [9, 10].

3. The relationship between quantum fluctuation and vacuum entanglement structure. A promising model is holographic random tensor networks [11]. The inflationary universe inspires us to construct self-breathing tensor networks driven by their own randomness, which might be the origin of uncertainty principle. The energy-time uncertainty relation plays a fundamental role in our theory scheme, and we wonder if a derivation of it is possible, and we expect the derivation of various generalized (information or gravitational perspective) uncertainty relations [12–14].

4. Inspired by the theory of quantum vacuum fluctuation engine, we might be able to establish an entanglement-energy conservation law. Virtual particles in the quantum fluctuation can be seen as the spontaneous tendency of classicalization. The energy threshold for virtual particles becoming real particles could be related to the entanglement-energy conservation law. Landauer’s principle governs the minimal energy that must be consumed to erase a bit of information. Energy consumption corresponds to entanglement increase in our theory scheme. We expect an entanglement-energy-information conservation law.

5. We need to consider the compatibility between measurement-induced locality and quantum error correc-

tion code (QECC) locality, which claims that locality and the speed of light are not exactly true, but it effectively holds for all local observers that do not have the ability to simultaneously measure a big part of the Universe [7, 15, 16].

6. Cosmological constant problem. It is shown that when the quantum to classical transition is properly treated, with due consideration of the relation of decoherence, noise, fluctuation, and dissipation, the amplitude of density contrast predicted falls in the acceptable range without requiring a fine-tuning of the coupling constant [4]. Recently, by treating the divergent vacuum energy density of quantum fluctuation seriously without trying renormalization, fine-tune problem is circumvented, claiming that there is no necessity to introduce dark energy [17, 18].

7. It has been demonstrated that the observed phenomena that are currently attributed to dark matter are the consequence of the emergent nature of gravity and are caused by an elastic response due to the volume law contribution to the entanglement entropy in our universe [19].

8. The universe is a spontaneous quantum vacuum engine. Our universe is the one and only ‘perpetual motion machine’ through spontaneous quantum fluctuation. Reminding that the early universe is the one and only observer, we conclude that a perpetual motion machine is only possible if it is not for utilisation. He just exists on his own with no other purpose.

IV Unfinished ideas

We should begin from a completely quantum regime, and figure out the classicalization process, to get a unified

theory, not only for physics, but for both physics and mathematics, and maybe this unification can be extended to biology (who are we).

The arrow of time. Quantum complexity growth might be a promising candidate for the arrow of time. By investigating the complexity of being entangled, the Complexity=Action conjecture might be a natural result in this theory scheme. An argument about ER=EPR conjecture can be given.

In our theory scheme, the uncertainty principle (quantum fluctuation) is closely related to entanglement. It was also argued that “the uncertainty principle determines the nonlocality of quantum mechanics”. In the classicalization process, when we establish statistical mechanics, entanglement should play a fundamental role.

Based on our theory scheme, black hole might be the original form of a universe because of its area law. Information loss and gain between multiverse. Parity-Time symmetric cycle, balanced gain and loss, and the origin of spontaneous symmetry breaking. Parity violation and chirality preference. CP violation and its origin in the context of multiverse. The meaning of time and its direction in multiverse. Relation with “To catch and reverse a quantum jump mid-flight”.

Conclusion: The proposal presents a summary of the ideas we aim to explore during the PhD program. Work is needed to concretize and substantiate this theory scheme. I am aware that research is difficult to predict, and this proposal will primarily serve as a starting point. I will follow where the work and results lead me.

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